

Catalytic Preparation of Alkyl-anilines. Part I.

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Methyl and ethyl anilines (both mono- and di-) are extensively used in the manufacture of dyestuffs. The usual method of their preparation consists in heating aniline with the corresponding alcohol and sulphuric acid in an autoclave at a pressure of 25-30 atmospheres to a temperature of 230-35°. This method has got two main drawbacks—

(1) That it is not a continuous method, and (2) that a very high pressure is, necessary increasing thereby the cost of production. Besides, the autoclave is required to be lined with enamel in view of the acid employed.

Attempts have been made from time to time to find an easier method of preparation by the use of suitable catalysts. Mention may be made of two important works in this direction.

(1) A German patent by Knoll & Co. claims that an almost quantitative yield may be obtained by heating aniline with the corresponding alcohol in the presence of a small quantity of iodine as catalyst to a temperature of 230°. In this case also the process is not a continuous one, and high pressure has to be maintained in order to raise the temperature to 230°. No mention, however is made in the original paper about the pressure required.

(2) Mailhe and de Godon claim that by using alumina as catalyst, a mixture of mono- and di-alkyl anilines is obtained by using a temperature of about 430°. They pass the mixed vapour of aniline and the alcohol over the catalyst kept at the temperature mentioned above. By passing the mixture a second time over the catalyst, practically the whole is converted into dimethyl or diethyl aniline.

The present work is an attempt to prepare the bases by using thoria as a catalyst. Mailhe and de Godon worked with this catalyst before but gave it up, the yield obtained by them was found to be very poor. The experiment was repeated and the

catalyst was prepared by starting with thorium nitrate and precipitating the oxalate. On burning the oxalate, the oxide was obtained in a very fine state of division. Three experiments were carried out with this powdered thoria at different temperatures and it was found that the percentage of conversion was rather low:

Temperature.	Conversion.
370°-380°	29 per cent.
430°-440°	40
440°-450°	43

So even at the high temperature employed about 60% of the aniline remained unchanged.

A modification was made in the preparation of the catalyst by depositing thoria in asbestos in the hope that better results might be achieved in this way as a greater surface of the catalyst would be exposed to the mixed vapour of alcohol and aniline. For this purpose, asbestos was first purified by digesting with hydrochloric acid and washing thoroughly till free from acid. Then it was soaked with a solution of thorium nitrate, dried in the steam-oven and then finally strongly heated, when the nitrate decomposed with evolution of nitrous fumes and thoria was deposited in a fine state of division. The results obtained by using this was quite satisfactory as will be seen from the following—

25 C.c. aniline and 25 c.c. ethyl alcohol were taken in each experiment, the amount of alcohol corresponding to the formation of diethylaniline. The results were as follows:—

Temperature.	Conversion.
350°-360°	68·4 per cent.
370°-75°	66·6
"	68·0
385°-390°	66·7

So even by using a lower temperature the yield is increased from 40 to 66 per cent.

The experiment was repeated with methyl alcohol, 25 c.c. of aniline and 25 c.c. of methyl alcohol being used. The results are as follows:—

Temperature.	Conversion.	Monomethyl aniline.	Dimethyl aniline.
410°–420°	72·8 %	32·8 %	40 %
„	67	29·4	37·6
420°–430°	75	45	30·0

Here also we find that the yields are quite good.

The percentage of conversion was determined in the following way.

A standard solution of the sodium salt of 2-naphthol-3:6-disulphonic acid (R-salt) was prepared by titrating with a diazo solution of aniline. The dyestuff formed settles down and a filter paper is spotted with the clear solution and also with R-salt solution and the end point is reached when just a faint line appears at the junction of the two spots.

Solution of R-salt was made by dissolving 3·7010 gm. in 250 c.c. of water. Aniline (1·4282 g.) is added to concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) and made up to 250 c.c. so that 1 c.c. = 0·0057 gm. aniline. 20 C.c. of this aniline solution is taken, diazotised and made up to 100 c.c. (1 c.c. diazo solution = 0·0114 gm. aniline).

5 C.c. of R-salt were taken in a beaker, a few drops of Na_2CO_3 solution and some common salt added and cooled. It is then titrated with the diazo solution. Vol. of diazo solution required = 9 c.c. Hence 5 c.c. R-salt = $0\cdot0114 \times 9 = 0\cdot1026$ gm. aniline.

Now in estimating the amount of aniline contained in the products, a known weight of the sample is taken and diazotised, the amount of NaNO_2 added being sufficient to react with the whole of the sample if it consisted of aniline solely—and then made up to a known volume. A known vol. of R-salt was then titrated with this diazo solution and from the volume of the latter the percentage of aniline in the sample was calculated. The results obtained are as given above.

Estimation of Mono- and Di-derivatives in the Products.

This was carried out in the following way :—

A known weight of the sample (1–1.5 g.) was taken in a 100 c.c. flask and treated with 5 c.c. acetic anhydride at the ordinary temperature. After standing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, 50 c.c. water is added and heated on the water-bath for about an hour to convert any acetic anhydride to acetic acid. By this means the acetyl derivatives of aniline and monoalkyl aniline are produced but the dimethyl aniline remains unaffected. After cooling, the liquid is diluted to a known volume and titrated with standard NaOH using phenolphthalin as indicator. A blank experiment is carried out at the same time using 5 c.c. acetic anhydride only and by difference the amount of acetic anhydride consumed in reacting with aniline and monomethyl aniline is ascertained. Multiplying the quantity of the acetic anhydride used up by $\frac{10}{97}$, we get the combined percentage of aniline and monomethyl aniline in terms of monomethylaniline (*a*). The percentage of aniline already found, is next converted into its equivalent of monomethyl aniline, multiplying by the factor $\frac{10}{93}$ (*b*). By subtracting (*b*) from (*a*) we get the percentage of monomethyl aniline. The percentage of dimethylaniline is finally obtained by difference.

Further experiments in this direction are in progress.

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